

Scientific article

Evaluating the potential of a wake steering co-design for wind farm layout optimization through a tailored genetic algorithm

Authors: Matteo Baricchio, Pieter M. O. Gebraad, and Jan-Willem van Wingerden

Published on: Wind Energy Science, Volume 9, 2113–2132, 2024

Abstract: *Wake steering represents a viable solution to mitigate the wake effect within a wind farm. New research that considers the effect of the control strategy within the layout optimization is emerging, adopting a co-design approach. This study estimates the potential of this technique within the layout optimization for a wide range of realistic conditions. To capture the benefits of such methods, a genetic algorithm tailored to the layout optimization problem has been developed in this work; hence this is referred to as a layout optimization genetic algorithm (LO-GA). The crossover phase is designed to recognize and exploit the differences and the similarities between parent layouts, whereas the randomness of the mutation is limited to improve the exploration of the design space. New relations have been introduced to calculate the geometric yaw angles based on the reciprocal positions between the turbines. For a base case of 16 turbines located at Hollandse Kust Noord site, a gain in the annual energy production between 0.3% and 0.4% is obtained when the co-design approach is adopted. This increases up to 0.6% for larger farms, saturating after 25 turbines. The benefit of the co-design decreases if the power density of the wind farm is lower than 15 Wm^{-2} or if the wind resource is highly unidirectional. On the other hand, in case wake steering is not applied during the operation of the farm, a decrease in the AEP up to 0.6% is registered for a layout optimized with the co-design method. To prevent the risk related to future decisions on the control strategy, a multi-objective co-design approach is proposed. This is based on the simultaneous optimization of the layout for a scenario in which wake steering is applied versus a case where wake steering is not adopted during the operation of the farm. We have concluded that the solutions obtained with this method*

ensure an AEP gain higher than 0.3% for a 16-turbines farm while limiting the loss below 0.1% in case wake steering is not applied.

Link to article: <https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/9/2113/2024/>

SUDOCO is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101122256). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.